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A Heart Open to the Whole World: Creating a World of Freedom, Love and Forgiveness Based on *Fratelli Tutti*

Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ
Jesuitenkolleg, Innsbruck, Austria

Abstract: The encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* of Pope Francis urges us to embrace everyone and everything with love, compassion and joy. After introducing the analogy of a mother with open heart, we look concretely at the issue of being warm hearted to the migrants, as Pope Francis has always been. Then we look at the need to embrace the whole world with both our hearts and minds. We also look at some techniques to do so. Finally, we argue that being open to God putting our faith in Him necessarily demands being open to the world, in spite of its brokenness and evil, and

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doing good to other unconditionally, as *Fratelli Tutti* urges us. The heart open to the world acknowledges the evil in all of us, without justifying it or ignoring it. The evil in all of us, with all

its harmful effects, calls for acceptance, forgiveness and reconciliation. We need to do all that we can to eliminate evil and transform its power for love and goodness.

Keywords: *Fratelli Tutti*, Open Heart, Open Mind, Embracing the Whole World, Migrants.

Introduction

Regarding the India and the world of his dreams, the Indian nationalist leader, Rabindranath Tagore wrote already in 1910:

Where the mind is without fear and the head is held high;
Where knowledge is free;
Where the world has not been broken up into fragments by
narrow domestic walls;
Where words come out from the depth of truth;
Where tireless striving stretches its arms towards perfection;
Where the clear stream of reason has not lost its way into the
dreary desert sand of dead habit;
Where the mind is led forward by thee into ever-widening
thought and action
Into that heaven of freedom, my Father, let my country awake
(Tagore, 1988: 35).

He was dreaming of an India, which is open to the whole world. Here the ‘arrow household walls’ refer to the barriers of class, caste, creed, colour, and religion that separate people. In the majority of cases, these are superstitious beliefs that serve no purpose. It refers to the artificial walls created to segregate mankind on the basis of their race, caste, religion, ethnic origin, or class. These differences sever people’s bonds. Frequently, these events result in chaos and rioting. The foundations of law and order have been shaken. There is a deterioration in peacefulness. Most importantly, a

country's productivity and advancement might be slowed or even halted. Additionally, other powers may take advantage of this opening to attack that country. As a result, we observe that these are invariably destructive to a nation. Thus, the poet aspires for humans to be free of such elements.

The most effective means of eliminating 'narrow domestic barriers' is to provide appropriate information and wisdom to individuals. Otherwise, they will be oblivious of the critical nature of cohabitation for a happy and peaceful living. Only true education can instil in people an understanding that divisions between people are meaningless and serve no purpose. Additionally, governments should take initiatives to encourage communal and cross-sectional harmony, such as holding fairs or exhibitions.

Given today's fragmentary world broken through identity politics and ideological interests, we are threatened from within. The "divide, destroy and rule" policy is found all over the world at the political, ethnic and bureaucratic levels, is threatening our sustenance and survival.

In this context, we want to explore the ethics of sustainability proposed by Pope Francis' (2020) recent encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, which gives us all a definite sense of direction and hope. The call to embrace the whole world, including the marginalised and the discarded, is the core message of its ethics of sustainability.

After introducing the analogy of a mother with open heart, we look concretely at the issue of being warm hearted to the migrants, as Pope Francis has always been. Then we look at the need to embrace the whole world with both our hearts and minds. We also look at some techniques to do so. Finally, we argue that being open to God putting our faith in Him necessarily demands being open to the world, in spite of its brokenness and evil, and doing good to other unconditionally, as *Fratelli Tutti* urges us.

1. A Mother with an Open Heart

Let us begin this exploration with the theme of the migrants which lie close to the heart of Pope Francis. In the face of a global migration crisis, Pope Francis has frequently urged governments to welcome immigrants and refugees with open hearts, not closed doors.

In July 2013, on his first official visit outside Rome after his installation as Pope, the Holy Father said Mass on the small Italian island of Lampedusa, near the Mediterranean Sea, where about 20,000 African immigrants had drowned over the last quarter-century. The pope described the awful condition of those who perished trying to find a new life in Europe as a “thorn in the heart,” and he lamented a “globalization of indifference” toward immigrants’ suffering (Wuerl, 2015).

Pope Francis has also condemned the “inhumanity” that has forced hundreds of thousands of Christians and other minorities in Iraq and Syria to escape as refugees from Islamic State extremists who have forced them to convert, pay a high tax, or face death. This wave of forced departure, he recently stated, “degrades the Christian presence in the Middle East, the region of the prophets, the earliest preachers of the Gospel, martyrs and numerous saints, and the cradle of hermitages and monasticism” (Wuerl, 2015).

Our own country’s southern border became a focal point last year after it was announced that 60,000 unaccompanied youngsters had fled Central America’s gang and drug violence and dire poverty in search of a better life in the United States. Nonetheless, a significant number of these vulnerable children were harmed along the way, including through various forms of human trafficking.

Pope Francis encourages, in his Message for the 101st World Day of Migrants and Refugees, which was commemorated

on Sunday, January 18, 2015, that, rather than global apathy, this global migratory crisis should be handled with “the globalization of charity and solidarity.” Nations and international organizations must collaborate to address this issue, he said, noting that the Catholic Church plays a unique role in this regard since it has always been “a mother with an open heart to the whole world and without boundaries.” According to the Holy Father, the solution is not merely to embrace migrants and refugees fleeing violence and starvation with “tolerance,” but with “a culture of encounter,” and to treat them with solidarity and respect as God’s children (Wuerl, 2015).

As a result, organizations such as Catholic Charities have been on the front lines in assisting immigrants. We see immigrants as brothers and sisters and fellow members of God’s family in response to Jesus’ command to welcome the stranger.

However, it is critical for all members of society to remember that at some point in our family history, we were all strangers seeking to be welcomed, and that our nation has a history of accepting newcomers. Such an inclusive attitude is what has traditionally made the United States great, by making strangers neighbours and welcoming their contributions to our country. Our history as a nation of people from every land has been enriched by the contributions of immigrants’ gifts, talents, and ethnic heritage (Wuerl, 2015).

As Christians, we are heralds of this blessing, reminding others of our shared humanity, that we are all members of the same human family. Thus, the United States’ bishops support the government’s attempts to enact comprehensive immigration reform and policies that uphold the rule of law, safeguard human life and dignity, and do not rip families apart. As Pope Francis stated, we cannot remain indifferent to the predicament of immigrants because they are our sisters and brothers.

The Holy Father finished his address by urging migrants and refugees to maintain their faith and hope. “Let us keep the Holy Family in mind as we fly through Egypt,” he remarked. “Just as

the Blessed Virgin's maternal heart and Saint Joseph's compassionate heart preserved the assurance that God would never desert them, may the same hope in the Lord never be wanting in you" (Wuerl. 2015).

2. A Heart Open to the Migrants

This friendly reception to the migrants is present also the encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*. A section of the second chapter and the entirety of the fourth chapter of Pope Francis' third Encyclical Letter *Fratelli Tutti* on fraternity and social friendship are devoted to the subject of migration. Chapter four is titled "A heart that is open to the world."

With their lives total "at stake" (FT 37), fleeing war, persecution, natural disasters, and unethical trafficking, migrants must be welcomed, safeguarded, supported, and assimilated.

The Pontiff maintains that unnecessary migration must be prevented by offering concrete chances for people to live in dignity in their places of origin. However, we must also respect the right to seek a better life abroad. In accepting countries, the appropriate balance will be struck between protecting citizens' rights and ensuring migrants' reception and assistance (FT 38-40; Borg, 2020)

a. The Unique Others as a Blessing

The Pope emphasizes several "critical steps," particularly in response to those fleeing grave humanitarian crises: increasing and simplifying visa issuance; opening humanitarian corridors; ensuring housing, security, and essential services; providing opportunities for employment and training; promoting family reunification; protecting minors; and guaranteeing religious freedom and social inclusion. Additionally, the Pope urges for the establishment

of the concept of “full citizenship” in society and the abolition of the derogatory term “minorities” (FT 129-131).

What is most urgently required – the text states – is global governance, an international collaboration for migration that enacts long-term planning, extending beyond single emergencies, on behalf of the supportive development of all peoples based on the gratuitous principle. Thus, governments will be able to think in terms of the “human family” (FT 139-141).

Others who are unlike us are a blessing and a source of enrichment for everyone, Francis adds, because they provide an opportunity for progress (FT 133-135). A healthy culture is one that is receptive to others while being true to itself, offering them something authentic. As with a polyhedron – a symbol important to the Pontiff – the whole is greater than the sum of its parts, but the intrinsic value of each is recognized (FT 145-146).

b. Politics Is a Worthwhile Type of Charity

The fifth chapter’s theme is “A better sort of politics,” which is one of the most useful forms of charity because it is oriented around the common good (FT 180) and values people as an open category open to discussion and dialogue. In some ways, this is the populism Francis refers to, which opposes the “populism” that denies the legitimacy of the concept of “people” by drawing consensus in order to use them for its own ends and fomenting selfishness in order to boost its own popularity (FT 159-160).

However, a more effective politics safeguards work as a “essential feature of social life” and works to ensure that everyone has the opportunity to develop their own strengths (Borg, 2020)

c. The Genuine Anti-Poverty Policies

The Pope argues that the best assistance a poor person can receive is not money, which is a temporary solution, but rather allowing him or her to live a dignified life via labour. True anti-poverty strategies do not seek to confine or neutralize indigents, but to advance them in the spirit of solidarity and subsidiarity.

Additionally, politics' responsibility is to find a solution to everything that violates fundamental human rights, including social exclusion; organ, tissue, weapon, and drug selling; sexual exploitation; slave labour; terrorism, and organized crime. The Pope makes a strong appeal to eradicate human trafficking, which he describes as a "source of shame for humanity," as well as hunger, which he describes as "criminal" because food is a "inalienable right" (FT 188-189; Borg, 2020)

d. Against Corruption

Francis also emphasizes the importance of a politics that says 'no' to corruption, incompetence, malevolent use of power, and a disregard for the rule of law. It is a politics centered on human dignity that is not influenced by finance because "the marketplace, by itself, cannot fix every problem": as evidenced by the "havoc" inflicted by financial speculation (FT 168).

Thus, popular movements have acquired new significance: as true "social poets" endowed with that "torrent of moral energy," they must engage in social, political, and economic engagement, but with greater coordination. Thus, the Pope asserts, it will be possible to transcend "with" and "of" the poor policies (FT 169 & Borg, 2020).

Another hope expressed in the Encyclical is for UN reform: in light of the economic dimension's predominance, which renders the individual state powerless, the United Nations' task will be to give substance to the concept of a "family of nations" working for the common good, poverty eradication, and the protection of human rights. Rather of endlessly reverting to "discussion, mediation, and arbitration" – as the Papal Document urges – the UN must promote the law of force rather than the law of force, by favouring multilateral accords that better safeguard even the most vulnerable governments (FT 173-175).

3. Embrace the World with Heart and Mind

Francis call to embrace the migrants is only a symbol of his call to embrace every disadvantaged section of the society. His is a call based on both his religious and spiritual vision that God has created all of us and so we are all brothers and sisters to one another. This urges us to respect each one of us, especially the poor and the marginalised.

In this section, inspired by the life-changing coach, Joseph Bernard (Bernard, 2012) we investigate how we can embrace the others both with our heart and mind, mainly from psychological perspectives. We all know that we are living in pivotal times that will influence humanity's and the planet's futures. Due to our particular capacities, we were born to be a part of this era. These potentials are only attainable if our brains and emotions are open.

Given the challenges we face individually and collectively, It is now high time for everyone to come forward with an open mind and heart. This openness is necessary for all of us to break free from the old, ineffective ways. Once liberated, we can collaborate to develop new, more expanded modes of expression.

Our social structures, commercial models, economic systems, human services, planetary activities, and political and religious groups all require new modes of expression. They could all work more effectively for the greater good of humanity and the earth (Bernard, 2012).

We must be great agents of constructive change, inspired by the Holy Father. The issue is how to accomplish this. How can we combine the unlimited flexibility and creativity of our open minds with the infinite loving wisdom of our open hearts for the greater good of all life on the planet? The task is enormous, the obstacles interminable, but happily, our options and potential are astoundingly incredible.

Are we capable of meeting the challenge? Of course we are; otherwise, we would not be on the earth at this same moment. Allow us to begin by putting our egos aside. We cannot allow fear

to dominate the debate. Increased power and control are not the solution. We will get nowhere by blaming others. We do not require further viewpoints based on failing ideas and ideologies from the past. Enough is sufficient (Bernard, 2012).

We require both clarity and compassion. We require the strength inherent in our highest consciousness. This will need us to slow down, tune inward beyond the chattering mind, to be mindful and alert, and to listen to our intuition and other inner guidance.

Fortunately, in these times of global connectedness, there are common practices that are available to everyone. There are numerous activities that bring us into the present moment, including meditation, mindfulness, yoga, tai chi, qigong, and contemplative prayer. Another approach to ground us in the present moment is through creative expression. Now is the time when genius is realized and solutions are imagined.

The heart's power is a critical component of the better-world puzzle. The capacity of the heart to love, to be kind, and to have compassion for everyone is critical. Without love and compassion, we are a merciless mob bent on survival at any cost, even the destruction of the future. The capacity of the heart to care serves as a counterbalance to the mind's ability to rationalize away past failures (Bernard, 2012).

Keeping this in mind, how do we go from where we are now to where we need to be in order to function more effectively as a global family? Yes, it appears as though we do require salvation from the dread of our ego-mind and the dominant motivators of our day — money, power, and control.

Are we prepared to make a commitment to maintaining an open mind and heart? Are we willing to put in the effort necessary to keep both doors open? If this is the case, you may find the following practices beneficial.

Before we get to the practices, a final note or two: 1) Having an open mind and heart is more of a purification than it is a new way of being. 2) We become choked up by life, and returning to an open state is more natural.

These open states are accessible to everyone. They are more easily accessed during peaceful periods of reflection and awareness, in the unconditional giving and receiving of love, and in the flow of personal expression and purpose (Bernard, 2012).

a. Opening Our Hearts

These four heart openings will enable us to return to your heart's true desire to love freely and to embrace everyone compassionately (Bernard, 2012):

1. **Forgive the Past:** We must forgive the past, let go of any unfinished business from the past, and move forward. The past has passed us by, and it must be entirely released. Self- and other-forgiveness is really beneficial. Today is critical. Allow everything else to pass. In the here and now, a heart can love indefinitely.

2. **Express Our Own Feelings:** Our true feelings and emotions are frequently suppressed due to their overwhelming nature. If we merely acknowledge how we are feeling, those emotions quickly transform into another. Emotions can be communicated in healthy ways that maintain an open, giving heart. Speaking and journaling are two examples of healthy emotional expression.

3. **Shift from Judgment to Critical Acceptance:** A critical mind clogs the heart. We have been socialized to categorize everything as "good or terrible." We can put aside our judgments and work toward embracing what is, accepting diversity, and valuing the uniqueness of all beings. This restores our heart to its natural state of openness to the infinite flow of love.

4. **Sensitize Ourselves to the Feelings Our Own Body:** The body constantly communicates with us since it is either expanding or contracting in all of its interactions with the outside world.

Investigate what maintains the heart open and what causes it to close. With this knowledge, you can love where opportunities exist and work to transform bad situations into more hopeful ones. The heart desires love.

b. Opening Our Minds

The following four mind openers will assist you in maintaining an open mind (Bernard, 2012):

1. **Examine Ideas on a Regular Basis:** Outdated beliefs can sap your vitality. Guilt, self-doubt, and feelings of unworthiness are all learned thoughts that may wreak havoc on your life. The majority of beliefs are false, and many substantially impair our progress. Be cognizant of the beliefs that shape your experiences and evaluate them with compassion. Keep them if they represent the truth. If not, release them.

2. **Be Aware of Our Thoughts:** Your experience of life is shaped by your thoughts. Your best bet is to monitor your thoughts, to remain cheerful and optimistic, and to do all possible to remain present in the moment. You can let those thoughts that are contracting your mind pass right through. We can keep our thoughts open if we are attentive of our thinking. An open mind continues to expand.

3. **Recognize the Ego-Mind at Work:** The ego-job of the mind is to protect you from anything it fears. You can notice the ego-mind at work when you feel the need to be correct, when you become fixated on blaming and complaining, and when you need increased power and control. Additionally, the ego is adept at explaining why the intellect should be closed. Remove yourself from the ego's voice. Rather than that, be receptive to new possibilities.

4. **Discover Our Higher Mind:** This higher mind is the voice of the infinite and eternal Spirit that resides inside each one of us and in the world. You can refer to it as the soul's voice,

your intuition, or your wise intellect. It is accessed by interior listening, by being receptive to instruction, and by living in the present moment. This knowledgeable intellect is inextricably linked to the wisdom of the entire human race and the Universe. This voice has everything you will ever need to know. All we have to do is be receptive to the power of God (Bernard, 2012).

We can develop strategies for incorporating more mental and emotional openness into your manner of being in the world. Our free and complete expression is far more significant than we may know.

We can spread compassion, consciousness, peace, and joy in a world filled with grief, suffering, and rejection by having open minds and hearts. All of our issues and difficulties can be resolved creatively and resourcefully in this expanded state of awareness (Bernard, 2012).

After having open our hearts and mind to others and to the world, we shall explore some techniques to open and embrace the world with all its shortcomings and frailties.

4. Some Techniques to Open Ourselves to the World

When terrible experiences occur in our lives, we frequently wall ourselves off; rather than allowing the world to soften us, we allow it to drive us deeper into ourselves. We attempt to divert the grief and pain by pretending they do not exist, but no matter how hard we try, we will never be able to escape from ourselves. We must learn to open our hearts to life's possibilities and allow the world to soften us.

When our concerns and seriousness begin to overwhelm us, we should take a step back and reassess our behaviour pattern. The following are seven ways in which we can more totally and completely open our heart based on the lifehacker, Kevin Wood (Wood, 2013).

a. Breathe into the Pain

Whenever a terrible event happens in our life, attempt to accept it rather than fleeing or masking the suffering. Take a deep breath and lean into the melancholy as it strikes. When we flee from the blossoming sadness in our life, it grows stronger and more genuine. We take a transient emotion and transform it into a substantial experience, rather than something that goes through us (Wood, 2013).

By focusing on our breath, we can help to soften our experiences. Our lives will stagnate if we stop them, but if we keep them flowing, more newness and bigger experiences will develop.

b. Embrace the Inconvenient

We are all familiar with the sensation of anxiety. We are all aware of how dread makes our bodies feel: the strain in our necks, the tightness in our bellies, and so on. We can practice leaning into these uncomfortable feelings and allowing them to guide us in the right direction.

The initial impulse is to flee – to avoid confronting these feelings. By doing so, we isolate ourselves from the aspects of our lives that we most need to experience. When we experience this sensation of being extremely uneasy, we can do ourselves a favour and lean into it. Regardless of fear, we can act decisively and drawn by the Spirit of God (Wood, 2013).

c. Inquire of Our Heart What We Truly Desire

We are frequently at a loss for the next step to take, compiling lists of benefits and disadvantages till our eyes bleed and our brains ache. Rather than always using this strategy, what if we engaged a new aspect of ourselves that is not typically involved in decision-making?

Many a times we have all felt compelled to take decisions or activities solely on the basis of our “gut” impulses: when pressed, we can’t articulate why we did so - only a deep knowledge that it needed to be done. This impulse is the part of ourselves that we are seeking answers from.

To begin, take several long breaths and then inquire, “Heart, what decision should I make here?” Which course of action feels the most natural?” Consider what arises, then engage and analyse the result (Wood, 2013).

d. Engage with Our Own Shadow

Many of us on the path of personal development become obsessed with adopting characteristics we desire, such as happiness, compassion, love, and passion. In the process of pursuing this goal, we sacrifice aspects of ourselves that make us full, such as hiding our bad characteristics rather than addressing them. Consider the following:

What aspects of myself could I live without?

How do I obstruct my own progress?

Is there something that I’m concealing from myself?

Avoid being terrified of what comes out. We may want to flee the answers, but instead, acknowledge them and spend as much time as possible with them. Once we gain a better understanding of what we been concealing, it becomes easier to shed our light on it (Wood, 2013).

e. Follow Our Own Joys

We’re going to take a hint from renowned mythologist Joseph Campbell for this following step. A recurring theme throughout his art is the concept of following our bliss or joys. This entails embracing and trusting our utmost excitement, as well as allowing the deeper pull to lead us in a new direction, even if we do not believe we are ready.

The term bliss does not allude to perpetual happiness; rather, it is a reference to a greater calling. Confidence in this will carry us through difficult circumstances, and allow ourselves to be filled with our own joys and hopes

f. Invest Time in Solitude

We are surrounded by people for the majority of our lives: our friends, co-workers, peers, family members, loved ones, and strangers. How frequently do we truly spend time by ourselves?

When we spend time alone, we are free from outside influences and may genuinely open up and explore whatever we want. Take a look at where our thoughts lead us. The golden ticket here is to avoid distractions and simply experience what it's like to be alone.

It may be uncomfortable or even frightening at first, but by allowing ourselves to experience these new emotions, we will add a new layer of depth, experience, and insight to our lives (Wood, 2013). "All of humanity's problems stem from man's inability to sit quietly in a room alone," observed Blaise Pascal (1670), a French philosopher. According to him, we fear the silence of existence, we dread boredom and instead choose aimless distraction, and we can't help but run from the problems of our emotions into the false comforts of the mind, especially during this pandemic times (Le Penne, 2020,

g. Expand Our Horizons and Get Involved

This may appear to be a contradiction to the previous suggestion, but in reality, they function in tandem. After delving into the depths of oneself, we emerge with a fresh perspective. Now is the time to share that with others – not by telling them, but by being with them.

When we are with a group of individuals, offer them our complete attention and energy so that we can understand them just as well as we understood ourselves. Consider their distinctiveness as if they were an extension of our own selves. Allow ourselves to be carried away by the beauty of others; consider what they might tell we about ourselves.

Bear in mind that we do not have to complete all of these at the same time. Take each one day by day, determining which ones work best for us, and see what we uncover (Wood, 2013). But we trust in the divine Goodness and follow the promptings of the Spirit, we will learn to embrace the world and rejoice in it, in spite of the pains and setbacks we may experience.

Si we are called to be involved in our world, to attempt to change it for the better. We are challenged to be the change that the world needs. As religious people we can base ourselves on the psychological tips and life-hacking techniques and go further. We need to recognise the spiritual basis that God is our common Father and we are truly brothers and sisters. On that firm spiritual basis, it will be easier for us to embrace the others, in spite of the selfishness, brokenness and even evil present in them, recognising at the same time that we too have the same tendencies within ourselves. C. S. Lewis (1980) reminds us, “To be a Christian means to forgive the inexcusable, because God has forgiven the inexcusable in you.”

Concluding Remarks

The challenge for us to open to the world and to embrace is comes directly from our openness to God, as Pope Francis puts it. Pope Francis expresses his hopes and objectives for the future of the Church and the world in a fruitful dialogue with Father Antonio Spadaro over the course of 16 talks from 2013 to 2017. His influence on the modern world is astounding and humanising. He has flipped the Catholic Church on its head, thrown open the Vatican’s windows, and cleansed the Augean stables of simony,

nepotism, and financial skulduggery. But he is most concerned with the poor, the hungry, the migrants and the disenfranchised.

a. Open to God, Open to the World

Pope Francis does not sit in a Vatican room and write academic books. He maintains an open line of communication with the outer world and the international Catholic Church. He enjoys being questioned and finds it natural to react. This new book contains some of his most valuable dialogues with people of all types and backgrounds. Several of the interviews in this volume were intended to be private. Father Spadaro first recorded these free, spontaneous discussions for his own use, but upon re-listening, he was struck by “a vision of the church and a vision of the world” and collaborated with Pope Francis to bring this “rich vision” to a broader audience.

Open to God: Open to the World, an insightful book by Pope Francis (Francis & Spadaro, 2018) provides an enthralling peek inside the thoughts and workings of a Pope who is quite unlike any other. As these talks demonstrate, the Franciscan revolution is well underway, and despite Francis’s opponents, the revolution will continue and new vistas will be opened for the world’s Catholics and non-Catholics. Open to God: Open to the World is a challenging invitation, along with FT, to make the world more humane, sustainable and viable. It invites us to embrace even those who think differently and the shadowy and evil dimensions of the world through agapeic love.

For Pope Francis openness to the world is a necessary condition for being open to God and also the other way around!

b. Do Good Anyway

Thus as Christians we are challenged to be open to the others, to embrace them with their own difficulties and challenges. Here the ten timeless principles-first articulated by Keith Kent when he was a college student in the 1960s is relevant for us. It is his manifesto about doing good and embracing the other in a crazy, ungrateful world. These commandments are the basis of his repackaged and expanded book *Anyway* (Keith, 2002).

1. People are illogical, unreasonable, and self-centred.
Love them anyway.
2. If you do good, people will accuse you of selfish ulterior motives.
Do good anyway.
3. If you are successful, you win false friends and true enemies.
Succeed anyway.
4. The good you do today will be forgotten tomorrow.
Do good anyway.
5. Honesty and frankness make you vulnerable.
Be honest and frank anyway.
6. The biggest men and women with the biggest ideas can be shot down by the smallest men and women with the smallest minds.
Think big anyway.
7. People favour underdogs but follow only top dogs.
Fight for a few underdogs anyway.
8. What you spend years building may be destroyed overnight.
Build anyway.
9. People really need help but may attack you if you do help them.
Help people anyway.
10. Give the world the best you have and you'll get kicked in the teeth.
Give the world the best you have anyway.

Later, Kent himself has applied it to the Christians, since Jesus did it anyway (Kent, 2007). May all of us live like brothers and sister and embrace one another, so that we can enable an ethics of sustainability that thrives on our common good!

This necessarily implies that there is evil and brokenness in the world. When we embrace the whole world with love, compassion and authenticity, we do acknowledge the evil in all of us, without justifying it or ignoring it. The evil in all of us, with all its harmful effects, calls for acceptance, forgiveness and reconciliation. We need to do all that we can to eliminate evil and transform its power for love and goodness. That could lead us collectively to an India and world which is truly a “heaven of freedom,” as Tagore dreamt of! Then we would be creating a world of forgiveness, freedom, love and solidarity, where each one of us is needed and wanted! By God and by one another!

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Kuruvilla Pandikattu Joseph SJ, is Professor of Philosophy at Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology, Pune, India is currently on sabbatical at Jesuitenkollege, Innsbruck. Email: Kuruvilla.Pandikattu@uibk.ac.at | GND: 124567274 | ORCID: 0000-0001-9815-3707

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